

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE IX

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

September 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

GUIDANCE SERVICES OF CIT COLLEGES OF PANIQUI FOUNDATION, INCORPORATED

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1. INTRODUCTION

Students face numerous challenges in various aspects of their lives, including academic, social, emotional, financial, career, personal, and family, making guidance, counseling, and program services increasingly important. Guidance and counseling have become increasingly important due to the individual's numerous challenges in critical areas of life.

The Department of Education (DepEd) has implemented Guidance and Counseling, an integral program that plays a necessary and vital role in the educational system and students' overall development. The guidance program is a coordinated program of activities and services such as individual inventory service, information service, counseling service, testing service, placement service, follow-up service, referral service, and research and evaluation service, which are systematically arranged and laid out to assist students with their numerous problems in school. The guidance and counseling program will address and resolve the students' needs, challenges, and problems (Aguilar-Ramat, 2022, as cited in NEAP Professional Development). On the other hand, guidance is a service that assists the individual in understanding their potentialities, abilities, weaknesses, and needs. Counseling plays a central role in the guidance program, being considered as the "heart" of the program. This service aims to assist students in gaining deeper self-understanding and awareness of their problems. Guidance services comprise many support systems to help students with their personal and career development and education.

According to Chakma (2023), teachers, counselors, and administrators benefit from cumulative records about their students. The information acquired should be thorough, comprehensive, and adequate for accurate inferences. The cumulative record identifies students who require further assistance and allows teachers to adjust the teaching accordingly.

Guidance and counseling services are important not only for academic success but also for professional growth. Career counselors assist learners in examining various career possibilities, assessing their strengths and preferences, and arriving at well-informed decisions about their future endeavor. In connection with this, Eremie et al. (2020) study on the "Guidance and Counseling Services' Influence on Career Choice and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students in Rivers State", vocational counseling motivates students and facilitates their career exploration. It's critical to have a thorough understanding of the guidance services that can assist young people in making career decisions.

As stated by Mann et al. (2020), remaining in school for longer than ever, today's young people must make more choices regarding where, what, and the intensity of their studies. These investment decisions are becoming increasingly challenging since technology is transforming the way the world itself is so rapidly. Good schools will respond by encouraging young people to develop critical thinking skills about how their education is related to the labor market. Practical career guidance has never been this vital, and collaborating with educational institutions to assist young people in understanding professions and jobs assists educators in making learning relevant.

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These services are important for providing a comprehensive guidance program that equips students with the appropriate knowledge, attitude, and abilities. It provides support and resources to improve students' psychological strengths and overall health. A practical guidance program is important because it helps students' well-being and academic success.

Guidance and counseling programs and their services are important in helping students manage stress academically and in other areas of their lives. Guidance counselors help the learners deal with their problems, academic, personal, or even social, such as those of the family and the environment. Counselors must have exceptional communication abilities to communicate with the most challenging students.

Republic Act No. 9258 defines Guidance and Counseling as "the profession that involves the use of an integrated approach to the development of a well-functioning individual primarily by helping him/her to utilize his/her potentials to the fullest and plan his/her present and future in accordance with his/her abilities, interests, and needs."

The responsibilities of guidance counselors are broad and continually evolving. It includes orienting students across different grade levels, preparing guidance and counseling forms such as individual inventories and agreement forms, and administering and interpreting psychological and projective assessments for individuals and groups. In addition to these roles and responsibilities, they provide excellent individual and group therapy, make referrals to other government agencies, and organize program support with the community through non-government organizations (NGOs) or government organizations (GOs). Not only that, but they also provide career counseling to students and provide scholarship programs to students. The guidance counselor is crucial in the school's support system, providing many services to needy students Llego, M.A. (2021),

Delivering guidance services requires establishing a professional relationship between individual seeking assistance for his/her psychological concern and a trained professional who is capable to provide the necessary assistance. In addition, it is difficult for designated counselors to manage obligations in offering assistance to persons in need when they are not trained and do not have background in the counseling procedure.

According to American School Counselor Association (2022), noted that school counselors are equipped with unique skills and qualifications that allow to implement a comprehensive counseling program, which addresses the social-emotional, academic, and career needs of pre-kindergarten to grade twelve students. They are leaders, advocates, and collaborators, implementing systemic change to provide equal educational outcomes through the school counseling program. They also assist students in accessing external mental health services when needed. ASCA also highlighted respecting students' values, beliefs, and backgrounds while ensuring legal and ethical compliance. Furthermore, counselors must maintain appropriate professional boundaries and uphold high ethical standards.

A Civil Service Commission (CSC) survey found that counseling accounts for 25% of a counselor's overall workload, with 25% spent on follow-up sessions with students. Other services include information, career counseling, individual inventories, referrals, and research. Counselors must be trained in the same field to administer counseling programs. Guidance counselors are important in ensuring students have positive school experiences. They must have the necessary abilities to do specified duties while fostering the learners' well-being.

Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, Article IV, Section 27, regarding in practice of guidance and counseling that "no person shall (a) engage in the practice of guidance and counseling without a valid Certificate of Registration and a valid Professional Identification Card or a special permit; (b) make representations to the public or to third persons as a licensed guidance counselor during the time that the license has been revoked or suspended, and, (c) allow anybody

to use his/her license as guidance counselor to enable such unqualified individual to engage in the practice of guidance and counseling."

The basic principle of guidance must be emphasized, that it needs to maximize the competencies of the guidance personnel to improve the educational services for the students. To make the school guidance program more functional and practical, guidance personnel must be committed, receptive, and active in building the people in the administration and the students' total personality.

Guidance and counseling programs in educational institutions help students integrate their interests, talents, and values enabling them to reach their full potential. The study attempted to look into the impact of a guidance and counseling program on academic achievement among high school students in Toronto, Canada. A random sample of one hundred (100) students, fifteen (15) educator counselors, and fifteen (15) head educators was selected from the five (5) educational institutions. Based on the findings of the study, the following proposals were made. Instructor counselors must provide all services required for a guidance and counseling program. There is a need to increase educational counselors' training in guidance and counseling. Instructor counselors must employ students' positive attitudes to strengthen career counseling within their schools. To improve the academic performance of the region's educational institutions, the guidance and counseling program should be enhanced, Shizha, Abdi, et al. (2020)

Implementing a guidance program that will provide the most comprehensive opportunities possible to benefit every student is imperative. A comprehensive guidance program comprises various guidance and counseling services tailored to the students' needs.

Vostanis and Bell (2020) found that guidance and counseling assist people in becoming more aware of themselves and how they react to their surroundings. This process also assists children in determining the personal significance of behavior and establishes and categorizes goals and ideals for future behavior.

According to Dhami (2020), as cited in NEAP Professional Development, Guidance and counseling can help people develop an awareness of their talents and abilities, a positive view on overcoming negative tendencies, and the resourcefulness and self-discipline required to adapt to social changes. The primary goal of guidance and counseling services is to help students academically, socially, emotionally, personally, and spiritually. Despite recognizing the importance of guidance services, challenges still exist in many educational settings.

In Malaysia, the majority of counseling and guidance teachers, as well as school counselors, have received special counseling training. Most high school counselors have a bachelor's degree in counseling, with some pursuing a Master's. According to the Malaysian Counselors Act (Act 580), some school counselors have enrolled with the Board of Counselors to become professional counselors.

Counseling services are currently accessible to primary school pupils as well. Counselors assist students with academic, career, and social concerns by linking educational goals to future achievement.

In Kakamega, the study discovered that some problems affecting guidance and counseling include an unfavorable guidance and counseling atmosphere, insufficient finances for the guidance and counseling programs, and a lack of adequate resources to support guidance and counseling programs. Emerging variables like COVID-19 and technology have changed the landscape of guidance and counseling. Guidance counselors encounter various obstacles, including a lack of psychological materials, limited services on placement, and insufficient time to give individual counseling (Paras, 2021).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, several studies were done in the United States to examine college students' psychological health. Three national surveys revealed a decline in students' mental

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Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

health. According to an online survey conducted by Active Minds in mid-April 2020, 80% of students stated that COVID-19 affected their mental health, with 20% reporting a significant decline in their mental health (Horn, 2020). It is particularly troubling that 56% did not know where to get immediate professional mental health care. Another national research conducted from late May to early June showed that 85% of college students had heightened anxiety and stress during the pandemic. However, only 21% sought help from a qualified counselor or expert. Despite the high frequency of mental health problems, college students often underutilize mental health services. When asked about the barriers that kept them from seeking mental health services, students reported a lack of perceived needs for help (41%), preference to deal with mental health issues on their own or with families and friends (27%), a lack of time (23%), financial difficulty (15%), and not knowing where to find help (10%).

According to Arrieta et al. (2021), there has been a shift in stakeholder dynamics, with guidance counselors strengthening homeroom and guidance, holding mental health activities, and working more closely with class advisers, teachers, and academic heads during this time. Similarly, a 2022 article titled "Two years in: Reflecting on counseling during pandemic", published by Counseling Today by Webmaster, highlights that school counselors have been increasingly working as liaisons and emotional support figures, not only for students but also for parents and faculty.

Stear et al. (2021), in their study titled, "When schools go dark, school counselors shine", highlight the critical role of school counseling during a global pandemic. The research illustrates how counselors even went beyond; they communicate with students and their families, and they updated/improved their techniques by giving students and families through text messages, calls, and video appointments to fulfill the immediate needs of their school communities.

Paras (2021) conducted a study that examined the state, issues, and possibilities of the guidance program in nine public high schools across three districts in Northern Palawan. The subjects were 95 guidance workers, including six school administrators, 10 guidance counselors, and 79 classroom instructors. The data were collected via self-administered questionnaires. Regarding the availability of guidance services, schools provided counseling, testing, information, and inventory services. The guidance worker ratio is 150:1, and among the key concerns cited were inadequacy of experienced guidance counselors, counselors who were overloaded with guidance work, a lack of psychological materials, placement services, and en loco parentis, which recognizes the importance of guidance programs in supporting social and personal needs of the students.

School counselors have traditionally been expected to take a wide range of diverse and conflicting roles. The shortage of guidance counselors impedes the efficient execution of the guidance program, leaving a sizable section of the student body without proper mental health support. According to Bakar (2020), the shortage of licensed counselors has resulted in the deployment of teachers without adequate credentials as guidance teachers, potentially compromising the quality of mental health support. Furthermore, insufficient facilities and resources exist to develop and implement career advising and counseling programs. The student-to-counselor ratios in most schools limit the services that counselors may provide with their diverse range of unconnected duties.

According to Mababa and Fabella (2023), the notion of guidance associate was established to address the impact of the guidance counselor shortage. These individuals with a bachelor's degree and specific training in guidance and counseling could assist without being registered counselors. Similarly, the Department of Education (2024), to address the lack of qualified guidance counselors, the Department of Education, (2024) suggested a Professional Development (PD) program for guidance counselors to provide participants with the necessary knowledge and abilities to effectively support learners' academic, personal, career, and social development. Furthermore, the program's

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primary goal is strengthening guidance designates' skills, empowering them to deliver comprehensive guidance and support services. These services include counseling, orientation and information, individual inventory, referral, placement, follow-up, research and evaluation, assessment, homeroom guidance program, career guidance program, prevention/intervention program for specific target groups, collaborative activities, and peer facilitation, ensuring the alignment with the evolving needs of learners and the educational institution's goals.

According to a study by Mabuza et al. (2025), there was a lack of administrative support, financing, and parental involvement. Furthermore, time constraints are a significant problem for guidance and counseling teachers implementing the program. The study also suggested that guidance and counseling should receive additional support from school administrators, teachers, and parents, including increased time dedicated to the subject and financing for guidance and counseling programs.

Program evaluation is indispensable to ensuring the effectiveness of guidance and counseling services. Sandra Hearth (2023) emphasizes the importance of evaluation in developmental guidance and counseling programs, ensuring accountability and helping stakeholders make informed decisions regarding the program's future.

As Lenz A.S. (2022) notes, counselors play a special role in program evaluation. They provide direct services, identify local needs, amplify historically excluded voices, and simplify complex data for broader understanding. Counselors also promote inclusive planning, monitor implementation, and contextualize a program's impact within the broader scope of human development. In evaluating programs, counselors contribute to identifying areas for growth, advocating for social change, and highlighting successes to support continued improvement.

Assessing and evaluating programs is crucial. Daniel Stufflebeam introduced the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) evaluation paradigm, which can be employed. This review is designed to provide information to decision-makers. This model's evaluation components are divided into four categories: context, input, process, and product. In line with this, according to Setiawan, M.A., et al. (2024), who conducted a study exploring the effectiveness of the CIPP evaluation model in measuring and enhancing the quality of guidance and counseling programs in Vocational High School in Indonesia. Understanding the challenges and contexts of Vocational High Schools, the study highlighted the importance of a targeted and evidence-based approach to enhance guidance and counseling services by applying and testing the CIPP model in this educational setting. In addition, it aimed to generate actionable insights that policymakers, educators, and practitioners could use to strengthen counseling programs, ultimately supporting students' academic and personal development.

Improving Comprehensive and Developmental Programs was the first edition of Program Evaluation in School Counseling (Trevisan & Carey, 2020), a ground-breaking book focusing only on knowledge, context, techniques, procedures, and evaluation examples relevant to school counseling programs. This book has a detailed technique for evaluating school counseling programs and historical evidence to back up the foundation and utility of such evaluations. Chapter 2 addresses "why" program evaluation knowledge is necessary in school counseling.

To establish the accomplishment of the guidance and counseling program's goals, efforts must be made to collect evidence in the form of data that indicates success, which will then be reviewed and interpreted. This effort is called evaluation (Yastibas & Erdal, 2020). Reviewing these activities can be helpful for future guidance and counseling programs. If the program functions correctly, it may be continued, and what is lacking can be used to improve.

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Thus, the role of the counselors is critical in evaluating the guidance and counseling program, determining the level of goal achievement, how well the services are delivered to students, and how the programs and services help students in their academic and life in general.

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order No. 09 Series of 2013 "Enhanced Policies and Guidelines on Student Affairs and Services" section 14, Article VII, mandated that higher institutions of learning should offer guidance services, using an integrated approach to help students utilize their potential to the fullest. It also mandated that these services should be managed by licensed counselors (CMO-No.09-s2013). Guidance and counseling services in the Philippines have been professionalized. There are set principles and criteria on Continuing Professional Education (CPE) and implemented procedures necessary and proper for maintaining high ethical standards in the practice of the profession (RA 9258, Art. II, sec. Q & ff.).

Likewise, the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, also known as Republic Act No. 10533, serves as a cornerstone in developing the educational system in the Philippines. This legislation laid the foundation for the K to 12 programs, emphasizing the importance of guidance and counseling in enhancing the quality of education. The historical context provides insights into the roots of guidance and counseling practices in the country. This also emphasized the need for guidance and counseling to support the students' mental health and overall well-being. Additionally, research highlights that effective guidance programs can lead to positive psychosocial outcomes, significantly impacting student performance and well-being. The diversity of student needs necessitates a structured approach to counseling, which can only be achieved through well-implemented guidance programs within schools. This is in connection with the passing of Philippine Mental Health Act (R.A. 11036) was monumental in placing the issue at the forefront of everyone's mind, focuses on mental health promotion in educational institutions, stating that schools of all types "shall develop policies and programs for students, educators, and other employees designed to: raise awareness on mental health issues, identify and provide support and services for individuals at risk, and facility access, including referral mechanisms of individuals with mental health conditions to treatment and psychosocial support."

According to Savitz-Romer et al. (2022), school counseling programs improve a wide range of student academic and behavioral outcomes. Effective school counseling programs require a collaborative effort from the school counselor, families or parents, community partners, and other educators.

A well-organized guidance program is essential to meeting students' personal, social, psychological, and career development needs. The administrators should take a leadership role in developing the guidance program by giving initiative and support, both morally and financially. Classroom teachers and guidance counselors/ advocates should also be encouraged to participate in developing and formulating the guidance program, which is a collaborative effort to deliver a practical guidance and counseling program in school settings. Each has specific responsibilities and skills to build a supportive environment promoting student progress. Academic advising and placement, counseling, and discipline are all part of student affairs and support services, and college and career services for older students.

The researcher was motivated to carry out this study because of the limited awareness among students and alumni regarding the guidance services offered at CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated. During initial interviews with the alumni, many expressed that they perceived the guidance office as only for students with complaints or those who cause trouble. Some alumni and current students were also unaware of the guidance services. Despite recognizing the importance of comprehensive guidance programs that provide academic, emotional, and social support, challenges still exist. A key issue is the limited awareness among students. CIT Colleges of Paniqui

Foundation, Incorporated's guidance services for the school year 2024 – 2025 include individual inventory, information, testing, counseling, placement/career, follow-up, and research and evaluation. However, the institution is currently facing a lack of registered guidance counselors.

Administrators, principals, and faculty members are critical in successfully implementing guidance services. Through active coordination with the guidance office, principal, and faculty members can utilize student assessment results to gauge their students' needs and concerns better, making it easy for them to offer corresponding academic and emotional support. On the other hand, administrators ensure institutional goals align with the guidance program. By measuring the effectiveness of the services, they can look for gaps and take measures to improve the services. Through such a collaborative initiative, issues related to delivering guidance services, like limited awareness and resource constraints, can be adequately addressed, enabling a more helpful and holistic learning environment.

The researcher was motivated to advocate for more accessible, structured guidance services to help students thrive academically, socially, and personally. This aimed to ensure students could benefit from these services and help administrators improve them. This study's goal is not to criticize but to enhance the guidance services to meet students' needs and contribute to their development.

This research aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of the guidance services of CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated, which focused on how the students evaluate the level of implementation of the guidance services, the level of adequacy of the guidance services, the high school teachers, and principal identifying the challenges encountered in the delivery of the guidance services, and areas for improvement.

Evaluation of the program involved those who were affected or participants who directly received the services. These were the students, the high school teachers, and the principal, who have direct contact with the needs of the students. Evaluation could also determine which services need to be strengthened.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to evaluate the Guidance Services of CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated. Findings of the study would serve as opportunities for improvements that could be proposed to improve the delivery of guidance services.

As such, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How is the level of implementation of the guidance services described?
 - 1.1 Individual inventory services;
 - 1.2 Information services;
 - 1.3 counseling services;
 - 1.4 Testing services;
 - 1.5 placement services;
 - 1.6 follow-up services;
 - 1.7 referral services; and
 - 1.8 Research and evaluation services?
2. How is the level of adequacy of the guidance services delivered described in terms of:
 - 2.1 Sufficiency of resources and support; and
 - 2.2 What are the appropriate interventions for students' needs?
3. What are the common challenges encountered in delivering the guidance services?
4. What opportunities for improvement could be proposed to improve the delivery of guidance services?

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Conceptual Framework

The evaluation can be used as a starting point for a more accessible and effective guidance service and to determine how people use these services. This study utilized the CIPP Model by Stufflebeam to evaluate the effectiveness of the Guidance Services of CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated. The CIPP Model (Context, Input, Process, and Product) is a widely recognized framework that comprehensively evaluates educational programs.

Similarly, a research study by Setiawan, M.A., et al. (2024) used the CIPP evaluation model to assess and enhance the quality of guidance and counseling programs in a Vocational High School in Indonesia. Their study highlighted the importance of using a targeted and evidence-based approach in the educational setting. The application and testing of the CIPP evaluation model aimed to generate actionable insights that policymakers, educators, and practitioners could use to strengthen counseling programs, ultimately contributing to vocational students' academic and personal growth.

Figure 1 presents the paradigm of this study. Four phases were conducted to evaluate the Guidance Services of CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated, in the context, using a step-by-step approach to solve the research problem. The research sought to determine the effectiveness and implementation of the guidance services, adequacy of the guidance services, common challenges encountered in the delivery of the guidance services, which are the input of the study, the process are the survey questionnaire and the product are based on the results of the study, which served as the opportunities for improvement could be proposed to improve the delivery of guidance services.

In the first phase, context evaluation, the study assessed the implementation of guidance services, including individual inventories, counseling, testing, placement, and follow-up, referral, and research and evaluation. The goal was to determine if these services addressed students' developmental, emotional, academic, and career needs at CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated.

In the second phase, known as input evaluation, the study examined the level adequacy of guidance services regarding available resources and support and appropriate interventions for students' needs. This included evaluating the qualifications and numbers of guidance counselors and the sufficiency of facilities and materials, and if the intervention were adequate and effective in addressing students' needs. The aim was to ensure that the guidance services were appropriate and effective while identifying any gaps that could impede their objectives.

The third phase related to the process evaluation involved a critical analysis of the implementation of the guidance services. Using a survey questionnaire as the primary data gathering tool, this phase sought to determine how effectively the services were being executed. Additionally, the common challenges encountered in delivering guidance services must be identified.

Finally, the fourth phase, which dealt with the product evaluation, assessed the outcomes and overall impact of the guidance services on the students and the institution. The findings from the earlier phases were analyzed to evaluate whether the intended goals of the guidance services were met. Based on these findings, specific recommendations and opportunities for improvement were proposed. The goal was to enhance the guidance services and create a more supportive and responsive educational environment, similar to the objectives pursued in the study by Setiawan, M.A., et al. (2024)

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

This figure illustrates the flow of evaluating guidance services at CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated. It begins with assessing the level of implementation of guidance services, which encompass individual inventory, information, counseling, testing, placement, follow-up, referral, and research and evaluation. The next step is to determine the level of adequacy of these services. It also identifies common challenges encountered in the delivery of guidance services. Finally, the findings lead to proposed opportunities for improvement, aimed at enhancing the effectiveness and delivery of these services.

2. METHODS

This section presents the methods and procedures of the study. This aims to discuss research design, research locale, study respondents, research instruments, data gathering procedure, data analysis/ statistical treatment, and potential ethical issues that will be used in conducting the research study.

Research Design

To evaluate the level of implementation of the guidance services of CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated and identify areas for enhancement, the present study employed a quantitative approach, particularly a descriptive research design. This method facilitated structure

evaluation by providing numerical data while allowing for additional insights to support a comprehensive analysis. Survey questionnaires were distributed to students, high school teachers, and the principal of the high school department to gather quantitative data on the current state of the guidance services.

This method provided a comprehensive evaluation, numerical data, and an in-depth perspective. Statistical data analysis and a review of relevant literature were also included to offer a well-rounded understanding of the impact of guidance services.

Research Locale

CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated, is located in the province of Tarlac, within the Central Luzon region of the Philippines. Specifically, it is situated at 22B Clark Street, Barangay Poblacion Norte, Paniqui, Tarlac. This institution plays an important role in providing quality education and services to the students in Paniqui and nearby areas.

Figure 2. Map of CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Inc.

Research Respondents

The study involved one hundred ninety-six (196) junior and senior high school students, sixteen (16) teachers, and one (1) principal from CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated. With a total high school population of four hundred thirty-nine (439) students, the sample size was determined using Slovin's formula, which estimates the minimum sample size needed for statistical validity with an acceptable error margin. Slovin's method helps researchers determine how a large sample size is required to achieve reasonable accuracy of results (Ellen S, 2022). Random sampling was employed to ensure the participants accurately represented the population

The Slovin's formula is calculated as:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size

e = acceptable margin of error

One hundred ninety-six (196) students were chosen because they had directly received guidance services, and their feedback reflected the services' impact on their engagement and satisfaction. Meanwhile, all sixteen (16) teachers and one (1) principal from the high school department were included in the study, as they have direct experience and a deeper awareness of

the challenges encountered in the delivery of guidance services; their insights provided a comprehensive perspective on the effectiveness and areas of improvement of the services.

Research Instrument

Two questionnaires were developed for teachers, the principal, and students. The questionnaire for teachers and the principal primarily focused on the common challenges faced in delivering guidance services. In contrast, the student questionnaire was divided into two parts and translated into Tagalog for better understanding. The first part assessed the level of implementation of the guidance services, while the second part evaluated the level of adequacy of those services.

The researcher adapted the Guidance Services Evaluation Form from Cura (2011) with some modifications. The survey aimed to address the significant objectives of the study, which included: the level of implementation of guidance services (such as Individual Inventory, Information, Counseling, Testing, Placement, Follow-up, Referral, and Research and Evaluation), the level of adequacy of these services in terms of the sufficiency of resources and support, and the appropriate interventions for students' needs. Additionally, the study aimed to identify common challenges encountered in delivering guidance services and to propose opportunities for improvement based on the findings. This research instrument was validated by experts in the field.

Data Gathering Procedure

In conducting this study, the researcher followed a systematic process.

First, a request letter was submitted to the principal of CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated, seeking approval to conduct the study. Once permission was granted, the researcher explained the purpose of the study to the respondents and obtained informed consent. For minor respondents, parental or guardian consent was also secured.

The study used survey questionnaires as the method for data collection. Clear instructions were provided on how to complete the questionnaires. Additionally, the researcher asked questions before and after giving these instructions. The respondents completed the surveys during their class period, and the researcher personally administered the questionnaires.

To encourage engagement and participation, the researcher explained the purpose and significance of the study to the respondents. Measures were taken to ensure that participants understood the scope of the study. The decision to reveal names was left to the participants, and the researcher assured them that their safety and well-being would be prioritized during the data collection process. All information collected was handled with full consent and confidentiality, used solely for academic purposes. In accordance with Section 8 of the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which emphasizes the importance of keeping personal information confidential, deliberate steps were taken to safeguard this information.

Finally, the researcher expressed gratitude to the respondents for their time and participation in the study.

Data Analysis

The researcher tabulated and organized the collected data to present the results clearly. Then, the same data was subjected to the following statistical treatments:

- **Frequency.** The frequency of a data value in statistics is the number of occurrences of a specific problem identified in the survey questionnaire responses. It was used to determine the most and least common challenges encountered in delivering the guidance services as perceived by the teachers and principal (Statement of the Problem No. 3).

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- **Ranking.** As the data is sorted out, this tool is used to convert numerical findings that are modified by rank. It was primarily used in this research to assess how a particular item's link with a group is determined.

- **Mean.** This was computed by dividing the sum of all the observations by the total number of observations. The following formula was used to present the response options of the respondents, and the corresponding value was assigned to get the weighted mean of each item. The formula that was used was as follows:

$$\text{Weighted mean} = [f(4) + f(3) + f(2) + f(1)] / N$$

Where 4,3,2,1 = corresponding value

F = frequency of each response option

N = total number of respondents

- **Likert Scale.** A four-point Likert Scale was used in the survey questionnaire. To measure respondents' attitude, opinion, or satisfaction with the guidance services. Participants then decide which statement best reflects their feelings about the presented statement or question. On the other hand, Likert scales are designed to measure the range of possible responses in measuring the degree of agreement or people's feelings about a particular subject. Nevertheless, Likert scales are also prone to response bias. In other words, respondents tend to agree or disagree with all statements due to fatigue, social pressure, or some people's tendency toward extreme responses, among others. Likert scales are also highly utilized in survey research and prevalent in marketing, psychology, and other social sciences disciplines (Bhandari, P., and Nikolopoulou, 2023).

In this study, a Likert scale was used to measure the level of implementation of guidance services (Statement of the Problem Nos. 1.1 to 1.8) and the level of adequacy of the guidance services delivered (Statement of the Problem Nos. 2.1 to 2.2). This approach allowed for quantitative data for respondents' perceptions and experiences regarding guidance services.

The following interpretation was used to determine the level of implementation of the guidance services.

Index	Limit Index	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Fully implemented
3	2.50 – 3.49	Agree	Implemented
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Slightly Implemented
1	1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree	Not implemented

The following interpretation was used to determine the level of adequacy of the guidance services.

Index	Limit Index	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Fully Adequate
3	2.50 – 3.49	Agree	Adequate
2	1.50 – 2.49	Disagree	Slightly Adequate

records) had a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=3.16$), which is interpreted as implemented. At the same time, the lowest score was in the administration of the cumulative or individual inventory record, which had a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.90$), interpreted as implemented. A study conducted by Chakma (2023) emphasized that cumulative records about students provide helpful information to teachers, counselors, and administrators. Proper administration of cumulative records was important for students to understand better. Information gathered should be complete, comprehensive, and adequate to draw valid inferences. The cumulative record indicated the students who had exceptional help, which served for future intervention and adjustment of the teaching accordingly.

Overall, the weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=3.06$) indicated that the individual inventory service was generally implemented in the institution. The results highlighted the need for better communication with students about record management, and it is essential to have proper administration of cumulative or individual inventory records, provide transparency, and ensure students are fully informed about how their records are managed.

3.1.2 Information Service

Information Service had various methods and programs to assist students in their personal/social, educational, and career development. It creates awareness of current information for better decision-making (CMO-No.09-s2013).

Table 2. Information Service

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I can access informational materials about scholarships, work immersion programs, job opportunities, and requirements. <i>(Ako ay may access sa mga materyales na naglalaman ng impormasyon tungkol sa scholarships, work immersion, mga oportunidad at pangangailangan sa trabaho.)</i>	2.97	Agree	Implemented
I attend or know about resource speakers invited to discuss topics such as study habits, stress management, personality development, occupational information, and other topics that may help the students. <i>(Ako ay dumadalo o may kaalaman sa mga talakayan tungkol sa iba't ibang paksa tulad ng study habits, stress management, personality development, at impormasyong panghanapbuhay na makakatulong sa mga estudyante.)</i>	2.91	Agree	Implemented
I see bulletin boards with guidance-related information on the campus. <i>(Ako ay nakakakita ng bulletin boards sa paaralan na naglalaman ng impormasyon tungkol sa guidance services.)</i>	2.88	Agree	Implemented
I notice posters, charts, and exhibits about guidance services and institutional programs/activities. <i>(Ako ay nakakapansin ng mga posters, charts, at exhibit tungkol sa guidance services at mga programa/aktibidad ng paaralan.)</i>	2.98	Agree	Implemented
Grand Mean	2.94	Agree	Implemented

Table 2 presents the evaluation of the implementation of the information service within the institution. The results revealed differences in the highest and lowest ratings, pointing to the areas where improvements could be proposed.

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The presence of posters, charts, and exhibits about guidance services and institutional programs/activities had a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.98$), which is interpreted as implemented. Additionally, bulletin boards, posters, charts, and exhibits were regarded as practical tools for disseminating information related to guidance services, with posters and exhibits receiving a more favorable rating from students. On the other hand, a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.88$) to the feature of bulletin boards with guidance-related information, although this rating still falls under the interpretation of implementation. The relatively low rating suggested that, while bulletin boards were present, some students might not find them as accessible or engaging. This could be due to placement or student preference for more visually appealing formats.

In connection with a study by Active Minds in mid-April 2020, 56% did not know where to get immediate professional mental health care. Similarly, another national research conducted from late May to early June 2020 showed that college students often underutilize mental health services, with 10% reporting not knowing where to seek help. This emphasizes how crucial it is to provide guidance-related information in a way that is visible, accessible, and engaging in order to increase the student's awareness or knowledge and use of the services that were offered in the institution.

Overall, the weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.94$) indicated that the information service was generally implemented in the institution. However, slight potential areas for improvement include raising student awareness and engagement with available informational materials. This underscores the importance of implementing the service and ensuring that the students effectively utilize it.

3.1.3 Counseling Service

The counseling services, being considered as the "heart" of the guidance program, play a crucial role in assisting students in gaining deeper self-understanding and awareness of their problems. Individual and/or group intervention is designed to facilitate positive change in student behavior, feelings, and attitudes (CMO-No.09-s2013).

Given the sensitive nature of counseling, particularly in extreme cases, those providing these services must meet the necessary qualifications. Similarly, according to Republic Act No. 9258, also known as the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, Article IV, Section 27, regarding the practice of guidance and counseling that "no person shall (a) engage in the practice of guidance and counseling without a valid Certificate of Registration and a valid Professional Identification Card or a special permit; (b) make representations to the public or to third persons as a licensed guidance counselor during the time that the license has been revoked or suspended, and, (c) allow anybody to use his/her license as guidance counselor to enable such unqualified individual to engage in the practice of guidance and counseling."

The basic principle of guidance must be emphasized, that it needs to maximize the competencies of the guidance personnel to improve the educational services for the students. To make the school guidance program more functional and practical, guidance personnel must be qualified, committed, and active in building the people in the administration and the students' total personality.

Table 3. Counseling Service

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I or the students receive counseling from a registered guidance counselor, or know that qualified and licensed guidance counselors are available. (Ako o ang mga			

estudyante ay tumatanggap ng counseling mula sa isang rehistradong guidance counselor.)	2.90	Agree	Implemented
I observed professional attitudes of personnel in the guidance office and during activities. (Napapansin ko ang pagiging propesyonal ng mga tauhan sa guidance office at sa mga isanasagawang aktibidad.)	3.07	Agree	Implemented
I am aware that the guidance advocate responds to self-initiated counseling sessions. (Ako ay may kaalaman na ang guidance advocacte ay tumutugon sa mga estudyanteng kusang lumalapit para sa counseling.)	2.97	Agree	Implemented
I know that counseling services are correctly administered. (Ako ay nakakaranas o may kaalaman na ang serbisyong counseling ay maayos na ipinatutupad.)	3.01	Agree	Implemented
I trust that confidentiality is maintained in counseling sessions. (Ako ay may tiwala na bawat counseling session ay kumpidensyal.)	2.97	Agree	Implemented
I see or know that the guidance advocate complies with policies, regulations, and guidelines. (Nakikita o nalalaman ko na ang guidance advocate ay sumusunod sa mga patakaran, regulasyon, at alituntunin.)	2.94	Agree	Implemented
I know that counseling is available to all students during school hours. (Ako ay may kaalaman na ang counseling ay bukas para sa lahat ng estudyante at ito ay isinasagawa kapag may pasok.)	3.05	Agree	Implemented
I am aware of and participate in homeroom guidance sessions for students. (Ako ay dumadalo o may kaalaman na may mga homeroom guidance sessions para sa mga estudyante.)	2.84	Agree	Implemented
Grand Mean	2.97	Agree	Implemented

Table 3 presents the evaluation of the implementation of the counseling service in the institution.

The professional attitude of personnel in the guidance office and during activities had a weighted mean of (\bar{x} =3.07), which was interpreted as implemented in the institution. This high rating suggested that they felt or observed that the guidance office staff exhibited professionalism, positively contributing to the counseling service's overall effectiveness. Both ASCA's standard (2022) and the study's findings underscore that counseling professionalism requires empathy, cultural competence, and ethical guidelines to ensure students receive meaningful, developmentally appropriate, and confidential support. On the other hand, the lowest rating for some students was awareness and participation in homeroom guidance sessions, which had a weighted mean of (\bar{x} =2.84) and was interpreted as implemented.

Overall, the weighted mean of (\bar{x} =2.97) indicated that the institution generally implemented the counseling service. This indicated that the counseling service was generally seen as implemented. The lowest rating suggested potential areas for improvement, especially in raising student awareness, participation, and engagement in homeroom guidance session, in which this activity could provide students with the knowledge and skills they need to make their life more productive and meaningful,

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

and could be a way to determine the strengths and weaknesses of students that counselors need to put more focus on and eventually guide the students to resolve these concerns.

3.1.4 Testing Service

The testing service covers the administration of psychological tests, the collection and organization of updated test and non-test data to provide a comprehensive clientele background, and the interpretation of administered tests and other collected data for the students. Tests are not only tools and techniques used by teachers or guidance counselors to collect information about an individual, but they are also means for an individual to understand himself better.

Table 4. Testing Services

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I take or know about standardized tests (psychological, mental ability, and personality tests) administered by the guidance office. <i>(Ako ay sumailalim o may kaalaman sa mga standardized test hal. Psychological, mental ability, at personality tests na isinasagawa ng guidance office.)</i>	2.72	Agree	Implemented
I know that test and non-test data are collected and organized correctly. <i>(Ako ay may kaalaman na ang mga datos mula sa pagsusulit at iba pang assessment ay maayos na nakokolekta at isinaayos.)</i>	2.97	Agree	Implemented
I know that student data is used for planning programs and activities. <i>(Ako ay may kaalaman na ang datos ng mga estudyante ay ginagamit upang bumuo ng mga programa at aktibidad.)</i>	2.96	Agree	Implemented
Grand Mean	2.88	Agree	Implemented

Table 4 presents the evaluation of the implementation of the testing service provided by the guidance office. Students rated that the organization and collection of test and non-test data were collected and organized properly, with a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.97$) which was interpreted as implemented in the institution. The high ratings suggested that they felt or observed the processes involved in organizing and collecting test data were well-established and effectively carried out within the guidance office. The findings of this study support the role of the guidance counselor as described by Llego, M.A. (2021), which includes administering and interpreting psychological assessments for individual or groups and providing comprehensive guidance services such as developing guidance and counseling forms such as individual inventories, where this maintain students records, the result indicated that the counselor of the institution was effectively fulfilling her responsibilities in this area.

On the other hand, the area of students' awareness and participation in taking standardized tests had a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.72$), which was still interpreted as implemented. This suggests that not all students undergo these tests, which may contribute to their lower familiarity or engagement with this service; those who do not take standardized tests might have limited exposure or knowledge of the purpose and benefits of these tests. Enhancing communication strategies and providing relevant information to students about testing processes and how their data was used may significantly contribute to their overall experience and understanding of the services provided.

Overall, a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.88$) indicated that the institution generally implemented the testing service. In conclusion, while testing services were generally regarded as implemented, the

**World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

testing services within the guidance office might be improved by filling in the small gap regarding standardized tests and using student data for planning activities.

3.1.5 Placement Service

Placement service: This service considers goals, values, needs, interests, and capabilities in helping clients find a niche for themselves. Career and Job Placement refers to the assistance provided for vocational and occupational fitness and employment (CMO-No.09-s2013).

Table 5. Placement Service

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I receive or know that students receive assistance in educational programs, such as work immersion or job placement. <i>(Ako o ang mga estudyante ay nakakatanggap ng tulong sa pagpili ng programang pang-edukasyon katulad ng work immersion o pagpasok sa trabaho.)</i>	3.03	Agree	Implemented
I attend or know about "Career Days or Career Guidance". <i>(Ako ay dumadalo o may kaalaman sa mga aktibidad gaya ng "Career Days" o "Career Guidance".)</i>	3.05	Agree	Implemented
Grand Mean	3.04	Agree	Implemented

Table 5 presents the evaluation of the implementation of placement services provided by the guidance office. The highest rating on students' participation in career guidance activities, such as career days or career guidance, had a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=3.05$). This was categorized as implemented. The high ratings suggested that students observed or experienced career guidance activities that were highly effective and well-received by students, contributing to their overall career development and planning. On the other hand, the lowest in the area of students' awareness or receiving assistance in educational programs such as work immersion or job placement, had a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=3.03$) and was categorized as implemented.

Overall, a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=3.04$) indicated that the institution generally implemented the placement service. Although placement services provided by the guidance office were considered as implemented, there was still potential for slight improvement in terms of raising student awareness and engagement with educational programs like work immersion and job placement. Furthermore, enhancing communication and providing additional resources could help ensure students are more informed and involved in these opportunities. In connection with the study's findings, according to Eremie et al. (2020), guidance and counseling programs are essential for academic success and career development. Both studies indicated that effective career counseling can positively influence students' academic and career decisions. However, the guidance office must enhance communication, provide additional resources, and actively promote career-related programs to be truly impactful.

3.1.6 Follow-up Service

A follow-up service is a systematic monitoring to determine the effectiveness of guidance activities (CMO-No.09-s2013).

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
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Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I experience or know about follow-up sessions available for those who undergo interviews, counseling, or referrals, and proper implementation of home visits and parent consultations for exceptional cases. (Ako ay may karanasan o kaalaman na mayroong follow-up sessions para sa mga sumailalim sa interview, counseling, o referral, at maayos na pagpapatupad ng home visits and parent consultations sa mga espesyal na kaso.)	2.74	Agree	Implemented
I am aware that monitoring programs for academic progress and adjustment exist. (Ako ay may kaalaman na mayroon monitoring programs upang subaybayan ang progreso sa akademiko at adjustment ng mga estudyante.)	2.93	Agree	Implemented
Grand Mean	2.84	Agree	Implemented

Table 6 presents the evaluation of the implementation of follow-up services provided by the guidance office. The highest rating was in monitoring programs for academic progress and adjustment, with a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.93$), categorized as implemented. This rating indicated that students acknowledged the availability of this program. On the other hand, students gave their lowest rating to follow-up sessions availability, with a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.74$), also categorized as implemented. This lower rating indicated that, although follow-up service was available, some students might not be fully aware of this service and how this service can support them in their academic journey.

Paras (2021) also found that guidance counselors encounter various obstacles, including a lack of psychological materials, limited services on placement, and insufficient time to give individual counseling. These limitations impact the effectiveness of follow-up services; the lower rating in the present study for follow-up sessions availability may reflect similar resource constraints as discussed by Paras (2021).

Overall, a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.84$) indicated that the institution generally implemented follow-up service. While follow-up service was generally implemented, there was a slight room for improvement, particularly in raising awareness and enhancing engagement.

3.1.7 Referral Service

Referral services ensure that students receive appropriate assistance from the guidance and counseling or coordination with specialists to ensure that the special needs of students are met (CMO-No.09-s2013).

According to the American School Counselor Association (2022), one of the key roles of school counselors is to assist students in accessing external mental health services when needed. Furthermore, counselors must maintain appropriate professional boundaries and uphold high ethical standards.

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I am referred to or know about referrals when the needed services of the students are beyond the guidance and counseling services or expertise. (Ako ay na-refer o may kaalaman na ang mga estudyante ay naire-refer kung kinakailangan ng serbisyong hindi saklaw ng guidance and counseling.)	2.82	Agree	Implemented

**World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

I receive or know about information on agencies and professionals for referrals. <i>(Ako ay nakakatanggap may kaalaman tungkol sa impormasyon sa mga ahensya at propesyonal para sa referral.)</i>	2.72	Agree	Implemented
I am referred or know that students are referred by faculty, principal, or other concerned personnel. <i>(Ako ay na-refer o may kaalaman na ang mga estudyante ay naire-refer ng mga guro, punong-guro, ibang kaukulang tauhan.)</i>	2.91	Agree	Implemented
I know that referral processes are properly documented and coordinated with the appropriate professionals or agencies. <i>(Ako ay may kaalaman na ang proseso ng referral ay maayos na nadodokumento at naikocoordinate sa mga tamang propesyonal o ahensya.)</i>	2.89	Agree	Implemented
Grand Mean	2.84	Agree	Implemented

Table 7 presents the evaluation of the guidance office's referral service implementation. The highest rating was in the area of students' awareness, or knew that students were referred by faculty, principal, or other concerned personnel, had a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.91$), which was interpreted as implemented. This rating indicated they perceived or experienced that they had correctly conveyed the institution's referral procedure and ensured suitable referrals were made. On the other hand, some students, the lowest rating was on the area of students' knowledge about information on agencies and professionals for referrals, had a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.72$) and interpreted as implemented. This rating showed that some students may not be fully aware of all the external agencies and professionals available to assist them. The lower rating might indicate that information about the external referral service should be disseminated more effectively.

This is connected to the American School Counselor Association (ASCA) 2022, which emphasizes the importance of school counselors in helping students access external resources when needed. If students are unaware of these services, they are unable to benefit from these support services.

Overall, a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.84$) indicated that the referral service was generally implemented in the institution. However, no specific referral services were based on the institution's existing guidance program. The referral processes were mainly done through testing services, such as specialized tests administered to the students. This finding underscored the importance of formally incorporating referral services as part of or a component of the institution's guidance program to improve systematic and practical student support.

3.1.8 Research and Evaluation Service

The Research and Evaluation Service determines the effectiveness of guidance and counseling programs run in the school or institution, Mohalik (2020).

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Table 8. Research and Evaluation Services

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
I provide feedback or know that students give input on the strengths and weaknesses of guidance services. <i>(Ako ay nagbibigay ng feedback o may kaalaman na ang mga estudyante ay nagbibigay ng puna tungkol sa lakas at kahinaan ng guidance services.)</i>	2.81	Agree	Implemented
I observe that research and evaluation results are kept confidential and only accessible to authorized personnel. <i>(Nakikita ko na ang resulta ng pananaliksik at ebalwasyon ay sikreto at tanging awtorisadong tao lang ang may access.)</i>	2.93	Agree	Implemented
I am aware that research and evaluations are conducted to improve guidance services. <i>(Ako ay may kaalaman na may mga pananaliksik at ebalwasyon na isinasagawa upang mapabuti ang guidance services.)</i>	3.07	Agree	Implemented
Grand Mean	2.94	Agree	Implemented

Table 8 presents the evaluation of the implementation of the research and evaluation service provided by the guidance office. The highest rated area was the recognition that research and evaluation were conducted to improve guidance services, as evidenced in the weighted mean score of ($\bar{x}=3.07$) and interpreted as implemented. This suggested that students understood the role of research in enhancing the effectiveness of guidance services, which could contribute to the overall support system. However, the lowest rating was on their ability to provide feedback on the strengths and weaknesses of guidance services, with a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.81$), also interpreted as implemented. This indicated that some students felt they had limited opportunities to share their insights and experiences regarding guidance services. The slightly lower rating highlighted the need for a more structured feedback mechanism that would allow students to voice their opinions and contribute to improving guidance services. Likewise, a study by Lenz (2022) found that counselors play a crucial role in program evaluation by amplifying historically excluded voices and ensuring that all stakeholders, particularly students, are actively engaged in shaping guidance services. Furthermore, a study by Sandra Hearth (2023) emphasizes the importance of evaluation in developmental guidance and counseling programs, ensuring accountability and helping stakeholders make informed decisions regarding the program's future.

This emphasized maintaining confidentiality aligned with best evaluation practices, which could reinforce trust and encourage student participation.

Overall, a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.94$) indicated that the research and evaluation service was generally implemented in the institution. The school might implement more transparent research processes, ensuring that students understand how their input is used to improve guidance services. Additionally, increasing awareness about confidentiality in research findings could help students feel more secure in sharing honest feedback.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
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National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

**Summary Table on the Level of Implementation of Guidance Services at
CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated**

Indicators	Grand Mean	Description	Interpretation
Individual Inventory Service	3.06	Agree	Implemented
Information Service	2.94	Agree	Implemented
Counseling Service	2.97	Agree	Implemented
Testing Service	2.88	Agree	Implemented
Placement Service	3.04	Agree	Implemented
Follow-up Service	2.84	Agree	Implemented
Referral Service	2.84	Agree	Implemented
Research and Evaluation Service	2.94	Agree	Implemented
Overall Grand Mean	2.94	Agree	Implemented

This table presents the overall implementation level of the institution's guidance services, such as individual inventory, information, counseling, testing, placement, follow-up, referral, and research and evaluation services, which were generally implemented. The highest rated service was individual inventory, with a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=3.06$). This indicated that this service was well implemented, and student records were effectively managed and used for guidance. On the other hand, the lowest-rated services were follow-up and referral services, both received a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.84$). This rating suggested that slight improvement could be made to enhance the implementation of these services. Specifically, a need for more transparent communication regarding follow-up procedures and formally incorporating a referral service as part of the guidance program to ensure a more systematic and practical approach to student support. Strengthening collaboration between external support could enhance the referral process.

Overall, a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.94$) implied that, in general, guidance services in the institution were implemented; a slight improvement could be made to enhance the delivery of the guidance services.

The implementation of guidance services relies heavily on the roles of the guidance counselor. As Llega, M. A. (2021) highlighted, the responsibilities of guidance counselors are broad and continually evolving. It includes orienting students across different grade levels, preparing guidance and counseling forms such as individual inventories and agreement forms, and administering and interpreting psychological and projective assessments for individuals and groups. In addition to these roles and responsibilities, they provide excellent individual and group therapy, make referrals to other government agencies, and organize program support with the community through non-government organizations (NGOs) or government organizations (GOs). Not only that, but they also provide career counseling to students and provide scholarship programs for students.

3.2 Level of Adequacy of the Guidance Services

The adequacy of guidance services at CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated was assessed based on the two key areas: (1) Sufficient resources and support, and (2) appropriate interventions for students' needs. These factors determine whether the institution provides the

necessary structure and interventions to effectively address students' concerns, needs, and academic and personal growth.

3.2.1 Sufficiency of Resources and Support

Each guidance service had its functions and roles in responding to the needs of the students, which highlights one of the important areas to evaluate in this study, the sufficiency of resources and support.

Table 9. Sufficiency of resources and support

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
The guidance office has sufficient resources and staff to maintain and update student academic and personal development records. <i>(Ang guidance office ay may sapat na kagamitan at tauhan upang mapanatili at mai-update ang mga rekord ng mga estudyante para sa kanilang akademikong at personal na pang-unlad.)</i>	2.99	Agree	Adequate
I find that records, such as medical, academic, and psychological assessments, are adequately secured and managed to meet the needs of the students. <i>(Ang mga rekord ko tulad ng medikal, akademikong, at sikolohikal na pagsusuri, ay sapat na nakatago at maayos na pinamamahalaan upang matugunan ang pangangailang ng mga estudyante.)</i>	3.03	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office provides sufficient materials, such as brochures, career guides, and study resources, to help students make informed academic and career choices. <i>(Ang guidance office ay nagbibigay ng sapat na materyales tulad ng brochures, career guides, at study resources upang matulungan ang mga estudyante sa paggawa ng tamang desisyon tungkol sa kanilang pag-aaral at hinaharap na karera.)</i>	2.87	Agree	Adequate
The information about mental health, study habits, and career planning is effectively disseminated through bulletin boards, online platforms, and other means. <i>(Ang mga impormasyon tungkol sa mental health, study habits, at career planning ay epektibong naipaparating sa pamamagitan ng bulletin boards, online platforms, at iba pang paraan.)</i>	2.89	Agree	Adequate
The number of counselors and licensed guidance counselors is sufficient to meet students' needs. <i>(Ang bilang ng mga counselor at lisensyadong guidance counselor ay sapat upang matugunan ang pangangailang ng mga estudyante.)</i>	2.84	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office provides a comfortable and private space for counseling sessions. <i>(Ang guidance office ay mayroong komportable at pribadong espasyo para sa counseling sessions.)</i>	2.98	Agree	Adequate
Counselors are approachable and available when needed. <i>(Ang mga counselor ay madaling lapitan at laging available kung kinakailangan.)</i>	2.89	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office provides sufficient and updated standardized tests to assess students' academic, psychological, and career-related needs. <i>(Ang guidance office ay nagbibigay ng sapat at updated na standardized tests upang suriin ang pang-akademikong, sikolohikal, at career-related na pangangailangan ng mga estudyante.)</i>	2.96	Agree	Adequate

The administration of tests is properly organized, ensuring fairness, accuracy, and reliability of results. <i>(Ang pagsasagawa ng mga pagsusulit ay maayos at organisado upang matiyak at pagiging patas, tama, at maasahang resulta.)</i>	3.03	Agree	Adequate
The test records are kept secure and confidential, accessible only to authorized personnel. <i>(Ang mga rekord ng pagsusulit ay kumidensyal, at tanging awtorisadong tauhan lamang ang may access sa mga ito.)</i>	3.06	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office provides sufficient support in preparing students for career opportunities and further education. <i>(Ang guidance office ay nagbibigay ng sapat na suporta sa paghahanda ng mga estudyante para sa mga oportunidad sa trabaho at mas mataas na edukasyon.)</i>	2.89	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office conducts follow-up activities to monitor the academic progress and adjustment of students. <i>(Ang guidance office ay nagsasagawa ng follow-up activities upang subaybayan ang proseso at pag-aadjust ng mga estudyante sa akademiko.)</i>	2.89	Agree	Adequate
Home visits and consultations with parents are conducted for special cases that require additional support. <i>(Pagbisita sa bahay at konsultasyon sa mga magulang ay para sa mga espesyal na kaso na nangangailangan ng dagdag suporta.)</i>	2.85	Agree	Adequate
The referral procedures are well-documented and properly coordinated to ensure students receive the necessary support. <i>(Ang proseso ng referral ay maayos na dokumentado at pinag-uugnay upang matiyak na natatanggap ng mga estudyante ang kinakailangang suporta.)</i>	2.99	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office provides sufficient information about external agencies and professionals specialized support. <i>(Ang guidance office ay nagbibigay ng sapat na impormasyon tungkol sa mga ahensya at propesyonal na maaring makatulong sa mga estudyante.)</i>	2.99	Agree	Adequate
The faculty and school staff are informed about the referral process and how to assist students in seeking support when needed. <i>(Ang mga guro at iba pang tauhan ng paaralan ay may sapat na kaalaman tungkol sa referral process at kung paano matutulungan ang mga estudyante sa paghingi ng suporta.)</i>	3.11	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office has sufficient resources (staff, funding, and materials) to conduct research and evaluations that improve guidance services. <i>(Ang guidance office ay may sapat na resources (tauhan, pondo, at materyales) upang magsagawa ng pananaliksik at pagsusuri para mapabuti ang kanilang serbisyo.)</i>	2.86	Agree	Adequate
The feedback from students and teachers is systematically collected to enhance the effectiveness of guidance services. <i>(Ang feedback mula sa mga estudyante at guro ay maayos na kinokolekta upang mapahusay ang guidance services.)</i>	3.01	Agree	Adequate
The school provides adequate funding and support for research initiatives related to student well-being and development. <i>(Ang paaralan ay nagbibigay ng sapat na pondo at suporta para sa pananaliksik tungkol sa kapakanan at pag-unlad ng mga estudyante.)</i>	2.86	Agree	Adequate
Grand Mean	2.95	Agree	Adequate

Table 9 presents the observations or experiences of students regarding the sufficiency of guidance office resources, staff, facilities, and programs or activities. Out of nineteen (19) items, the highest rated item among students was the awareness that the faculty and school staff are informed about the referral process and how to assist students in seeking support when needed, which was reflected in a weighted mean of (\bar{x} =3.11). This was categorized as adequate. This rating suggested that the institution had a referral system, ensuring that teachers and staff were equipped to guide students toward the needed guidance services.

However, the lowest rated item among students was in the area of sufficiency of the number of counselors and licensed guidance counselors to meet the needs of the students, received a weighted mean of (\bar{x} =2.84), although this was categorized as adequate, the slightly lower rating highlighted the importance of ensuring that there should have enough qualified counselor to provide personalized attention to students. While, the institution had guidance advocate, Republic Act No. 9258 more popularly known as the Guidance and Counseling Act of 2004, Article IV, Section 27, regarding the practice of guidance and counseling that "no person shall (a) engage in the practice of guidance and counseling without a valid Certificate of Registration and a valid Professional Identification Card or a special permit; (b) make representations to the public or to third persons as a licensed guidance counselor during the time that the license has been revoked or suspended, and, (c) allow anybody to use his/her license as guidance counselor to enable such unqualified individual to engage in the practice of guidance and counseling." However, according to Mababa and Fabella (2023), the notion of guidance associate was established to address the impact of the guidance counselor shortage. These were individuals with a bachelor's degree and specific training in guidance and counseling who could assist in the absence of registered counselors, and this was present in the institution.

3.2.2 Appropriate interventions for students' needs

Appropriate interventions in guidance and counseling are essential to address the diverse needs of the students effectively.

Table 10. Appropriate interventions for students' needs

Indicator	Mean	Description	Interpretation
The guidance office ensures the confidentiality of all student records, and only authorized personnel can access them. <i>(Ang guidance office ay nasisigurong kumpidensyal ang lahat ng rekord ko at tanging awtorisadong tao lamang ang maaring makakita ng mga ito.)</i>	3.06	Agree	Adequate
The information from student records is used to develop effective programs that support academic and personal growth. <i>(Ang impormasyon ng mga estudyante ay ginagamit upang makagawa ng epektibong program na sumusuporta sa kanilang pag-unlad sa akademiko at personal.)</i>	3.07	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office provides timely and relevant information that supports student development. <i>(Ang guidance office ay nagbibigay ng napapanahong at mahahalagang impormasyon na sumusuporta sa pag</i>	2.97	Agree	Adequate

unlad ng mga estudyante.)			
Confidentiality is maintained during counseling sessions, ensuring a safe environment for students to express their concerns. <i>(Napapanatiling kumpedensyal ang counseling session upang maging ligtas ang mga estudyante sa pagpapahayag ng kanilang saloobin.)</i>	3.01	Agree	Adequate
The counseling services address various aspects of student development, including academic, emotional, and social concerns. <i>(Ang counseling services ay tumutugon sa iba't ibang aspeto ng pag-unlad ng estudyante, kasama na ang akademiko, emosyonal, at panlipunang usapin.)</i>	3.06	Agree	Adequate
The test results are explained and interpreted effectively to help students understand their strengths and areas for improvement. <i>(Ang mga resulta ng pagsusulit ay malinaw na ipanapaliwanag upang matulungan ang mga estudyante na maunawaan and kanilang lakas at mga dapat pang baguhin.)</i>	2.97	Agree	Adequate
The test results guide students in making informed decisions about their education, career, and personal development. <i>(Ang mga resulta ng pagsusulit ay ginagamit upang gabayan ang mga estudyante sa paggawa ng matalinong desisyon tungkol sa kanilang edukasyon, karera, at personal na pag-unlad.)</i>	3.03	Agree	Adequate
The guidance office provides adequate career counseling and assistance in choosing appropriate academic and career paths. <i>(Ang guidance office ay nagbibigay ng sapat na career counseling at tulong sa pagpili ng tamang kurso at career path.)</i>	2.97	Agree	Adequate
I have given access to information about scholarships, work immersion programs, and job opportunities relevant to my interests and skills. <i>(Mayroon akong access sa impormasyon tungkol sa scholarships, work immersion programs, at job opportunities na naayon sa kanilang interest at kakayahan.)</i>	2.97	Agree	Adequate
I find that placement services effectively connect students to training institutions, employers, or further education programs. <i>(Nakikita ko na ang placement services ay epektibong nag-uugnay sa mga estudyante sa mga training institutions, employer, o mas mataas pang edukasyon.)</i>	2.90	Agree	Adequate
The students find that follow-up data is used to improve instruction and student support services. <i>(Ang mga estudyante ay nakikita na ang follow-up data ay ginagamit upang mapabuti at suporta sa mga estudyante.)</i>	2.96	Agree	Adequate
Students who experience dropout receive follow-up support from the guidance office to address their concerns and possible reintegration into the school system. <i>(Ang mga estudyante na nag dropout ay nakakatanggap ng follow-up support mula sa guidance office upang matugunan ang kanilang mga alalahanin at posibleng pagbabalik sa paaralan.)</i>	2.82	Agree	Adequate
The students find that referrals are appropriately made when students require services beyond the expertise of the guidance office. <i>(Ang referral ay maayos na isinasagawa kung kinakailangan ng estudyante ang serbisyo na lampas sa kakayahan ng guidance office.)</i>	2.94	Agree	Adequate

The students find that referred students receive timely and appropriate assistance from the recommended professional or agencies. (<i>Ang mga estudyante ay nakikita na ang mga estudyante ni-refer ay nakakatanggap ng agarang at angkop na tulong mula sa mga propesyonal o ahensya.</i>)	2.92	Agree	Adequate
The students find that research results are analyzed and used to develop new and improved interventions for student support. (<i>Ang resulta ng pananaliksik ay ginagamit upang makabuo ng mas epektibong programa para sa suporta ng mga estudyante.</i>)	2.94	Agree	Adequate
Grand Mean	2.97	Agree	Adequate

Table 10 presents the observations or experiences of students regarding appropriate interventions for students' needs, which evaluates the effectiveness of guidance services in addressing students' concerns. Out of fifteen (15) items, the highest rated item was utilizing their records to develop an effective program to support their academic and personal growth, with a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=3.07$) and interpreted as adequate. This result suggested that the students' information was used appropriately to guide interventions. On the other hand, drop-out follow-up support from the guidance office to address their concerns and possible reintegration into the school system received a lower rating, with a weighted mean of ($\bar{x}=2.82$). Similarly, this aspect of guidance services received a lower student rating regarding its implementation. Although considered adequate, these findings suggested a need to strengthen follow-up services. This aligned with the study conducted, according to Dharni (2020) as cited in NEAP Professional Development, guidance and counseling can help people develop an awareness of their own talents and abilities, a hopeful outlook for overcoming destructive tendencies, and the resourcefulness and self-discipline required to adapt to social changes. The primary purpose of guidance and counseling services is to support students' academic, social, emotional, and personal development and spiritual maturity.

3.3 Common Challenges Encountered in the Delivery of the Guidance Services.

The effectiveness of guidance services is essential for students' holistic development. A counseling program aims to address students' needs and challenges (Aguilar-Ramat, 2022, as cited in NEAP Professional Development). However, various challenges can hinder their implementation. This study identified twenty common challenges faced in delivering guidance services at CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated, based on insights from high school teachers and the principal.

Table 11. Common Challenges Encountered in the Delivery of Guidance Services.

Indicator	Frequency	Rank
Limited budget for psychological test materials makes it difficult to properly assess and understand students' personalities, abilities, and needs.	13	1.5
Lack of private and adequate space for counseling sessions.	13	1.5
Limited awareness among students about the available guidance services.	11	4

**World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Difficulty in finding available specialists or being uncertain about which specialist or facility is appropriate.	11	4
Lack of up-to-date guidance materials, career brochures, and psychological tests	11	4
Inconsistent follow-up on students' concerns.	10	7
Difficulty addressing diverse students' concerns, including mental health issues, career planning, and academic performance.	10	7
Limited access to technology and data management systems for students' records.	10	7
There is a lack of registered guidance counselors to properly address students' needs, especially in severe cases requiring professional intervention.	9	10
Low involvement of parents in students' guidance and counseling needs.	9	10
Limited student participation in career and life skills seminars and workshops.	9	10
Limited budget for guidance activities and seminars.	7	12.5
Resistance from students in seeking help or counselling due to stigma about mental health	7	12.5
Difficulty monitoring the students' academic, emotional, and social development.	6	15
Lack of training and professional development opportunities for guidance advocates.	6	15
Lack of a structured evaluation system to assess the effectiveness of guidance services	6	15
Inconsistent implementation of homeroom guidance.	5	17
The heavy workload of guidance advocates limits the time for individualized student support.	4	18
Misconceptions of teachers on the role of the guidance advocate as disciplinary officer	3	19
Poor collaboration between guidance counselors/guidance advocates, teachers, and administrators.	2	20

The most prevalent challenges identified in the study were a limited budget for psychological test materials, which ranked 1.5, and the lack of private and adequate space for counseling sessions, which ranked 1.5. These findings aligned with the study conducted in Kakamega County, which discovered that some problems affecting guidance and counseling include an unfavourable guidance and counseling atmosphere, insufficient finances for the guidance and counseling programs, and a lack of adequate resources to support guidance and counseling programs. Emerging variables like COVID-19 and technology have changed the landscape of guidance and counseling. Guidance counselors encounter various obstacles, including a lack of psychological materials, limited services on placement, and insufficient time to give individual counseling (Paras, 2021).

Significant challenges ranked 4 include limited awareness among students about available guidance services. This was also observed during the administration of the survey questionnaire when some students expressed that they were unaware of the guidance services available. According to an online survey conducted by Active Minds in mid-April 2020, 80% of students nationwide stated that

COVID-19 affected their mental health, with 20% reporting a significant decline in their mental health (Horn, 2020). It is particularly troubling that 56% did not know where to get immediate professional mental health care. Another national research conducted from late May to early June showed that 85% of college students had heightened anxiety and stress during the pandemic. However, only 21% sought help from a qualified counselor or expert. Despite the high frequency of mental health problems, college students often underutilize mental health services. When asked about the barriers that kept them from seeking mental health services, one of the studies found that the student did not know where to find help (10%).

The limited awareness of students regarding guidance services may lead to underutilization of the guidance services. Furthermore, the institution faced difficulties finding available specialists or uncertainty about the appropriate specialist or facility. Another challenge identified was the lack of up-to-date guidance materials, career brochures, and psychological tests, which further hindered the effectiveness of guidance services.

Moderately ranked challenges, which were ranked at 7, include inconsistent follow-up on students' concerns. This guidance service also received a lower score in terms of implementation and adequacy, as rated by high school teachers, principals, and students. Other challenges included limited access to technology and data management systems for student records and difficulty addressing diverse student concerns, including mental health issues, career planning, and academic performance.

Challenges such as a lack of registered guidance counselors to properly address students' needs, especially in severe cases that require professional intervention, low involvement of parents in students' guidance and counseling needs, and limited student participation in career and life skills seminars and workshops also affect the effectiveness of guidance services. These challenges ranked at 10. In connection with the findings, a study by Paras (2021) examined the status, problems, and prospects of the guidance program in nine public high schools across three districts of Northern Palawan. The study found that while schools provided counseling, testing, information, and inventory services, they face significant challenges, such as a shortage of experienced guidance counselors. These counselors were overloaded with guidance work, a lack of psychological materials, and placement services. Similarly, this study identified a lack of registered guidance counselors as a challenge, especially in severe cases that require professional intervention.

Other challenges include a limited budget for guidance activities and seminars, resistance from students in seeking help or counseling due to stigma about mental health, both of which are ranked at 12.5. Additionally, challenges such as difficulty in monitoring the students' academic, emotional, and social development, lack of training and professional development opportunities for guidance advocates, and lack of a structured evaluation system to assess the effectiveness of guidance services were ranked at 15. A Civil Service Commission (CSC) study emphasized that those trained in the same field must conduct counseling programs effectively. In this context, guidance counselors are important in ensuring students undergo positive educational experiences. They must have the necessary competencies to perform assigned duties and promote the learners' well-being. Addressing these gaps would contribute to more effective guidance services that meet the students' evolving needs.

The least frequently encountered challenges were the inconsistent implementation of homeroom guidance, ranked 17, the heavy workload of the guidance advocate, which limits the time for individualized student support, ranked 18, and misconceptions of teachers on the role of the guidance advocate as a disciplinary officer, ranked 19—lastly, poor collaboration between guidance counselor/guidance advocate, teachers and administrators which ranked 20. Although ranked lower,

**World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
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 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

these challenges still require attention to enhance the effectiveness of guidance services within the institution.

3.4 Opportunities for Improvement to the Delivery of Guidance Services

Based on the challenges encountered in the delivery of the guidance services, identified by high school teachers and principals, several opportunities for improvement were proposed by the researcher to enhance the delivery of the guidance services within the institution, and despite the overall interpretation of guidance services as implemented and adequate, notable issues brought attention to areas that need improvement.

Areas of Concern	Opportunity for Improvements
Limited budget for psychological test materials makes it difficult to properly assess and understand students' personalities, abilities, and needs.	Include psychological testing needs in the institution's budget proposals. Seek partnerships to recognize a psychological testing service in the Philippines. (e.g., Philippine Psychological Corporation, Centile Psychological Assessments Services) which provides psychological testing materials and online psychological testing services for schools and work industries.
Lack of private and adequate space for counseling sessions.	Meet or address the private space for counseling by designating a dedicated and soundproof counseling area or optimizing existing spaces that ensure privacy.
Limited awareness among students about the available guidance services.	Regular orientations (e.g., general and departmentalized orientation, homeroom guidance), online platforms, and interactive discussions could improve students' engagement and awareness.
Difficulty in finding available specialists or being uncertain about which specialist or facility is appropriate.	Establishing a well-documented external referral system and maintaining a database of specialists (e.g., psychologists, psychiatrists) could help address students' concerns beyond the scope of guidance and counseling services.
Lack of up-to-date guidance materials, career brochures, and psychological tests	Updating resources and collaborating with educational institutions or other government agencies about job opportunities (e.g., PESO, DOLE) could provide students with more relevant information and materials to support their academic and career planning.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study investigated the effectiveness of the guidance services provided at CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation, Incorporated, focusing on how students perceived the level of implementation and adequacy of these services. The high school teachers and principal identify common challenges in delivering guidance services and explore potential areas for improvement. The results revealed that while key guidance services were implemented and adequate, certain areas, such as budget constraints for psychological testing materials, insufficient space for counseling areas, and a lack of a formal external referral system, were identified. Based on these findings, the study offers several recommendations for improving the services offered in the institution, including increasing the budget for psychological testing materials, enhancing the physical infrastructure for the counseling area, fostering partnerships with external mental health professionals, and hiring licensed guidance counselor.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The level of implementation of Guidance Services at CIT Colleges of Paniqui Foundation Incorporated, in terms of individual inventory, information, counseling, testing, placement, follow-up, referral, and research and evaluation services, is implemented.
2. Sufficient resources, support, and appropriate intervention for students' needs are adequate.
3. Limited budget for psychological test materials and lack of private and adequate space for counseling services are the common challenges encountered in delivering the Guidance Services.
4. An opportunity for improvement to deliver Guidance Services is proposed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered to enhance the delivery of the guidance services:

1. Regularly assess the effectiveness of the implemented guidance services in the institution by conducting a needs assessment for students and evaluating the guidance services each school year to ensure that these meet the students' evolving needs.
2. Despite adequate resources, staff, and interventions, hiring a licensed guidance counselor would improve service quality and ensure legal compliance. Additionally, establishing an external referral system to mental health professionals (e.g., psychologists, psychiatrists) would help address the students' concerns beyond the scope of the guidance and counseling services.
3. Increase or allocate budget for psychological test materials to enhance the quality of student assessments.
4. Establish a dedicated, private counseling area for counseling sessions to ensure a comfortable and confidential student environment.

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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue IX (September 2025), pp.276-309, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17247540

